

Schiff base complex formation by cobalt(II) and nickel(II) with 2-pyridine-carboxaldehyde and some bidentate amino acids

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Manuscript received 10 February 1999, revised 10 May 1999, accepted 23 June 1999

MAB, MA₂B and MA₂B₂ types of Schiff base complexes have been detected in the Co^{II}- and Ni^{II}-2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde (A)-L-valine, -L-phenylalanine and -DL-tryptophan (B) systems. Both the stability constant and absorption maximum values indicate that these complexes can be represented respectively as M(AB), M(AB)A and M(AB)₂, where the Schiff base (AB) binds the metal in a terdentate manner.

2-Pyridinecarboxaldehyde and its hydrazones are used as effective soman antidote for cyanide poisoning¹. It has been reported² that imino derivatives of 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde can be used as chemotherapeutic drugs. The Schiff base complexes derived from 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde and amino acids are powerful chelates and they exhibit antibacterial activities^{3,4}. The literature survey indicates that the reports on the solution complexes of the Schiff bases derived from 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde are very few⁴. The present communication reports the results of the solution equilibria of Co^{II}- and Ni^{II}-2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde (pyal) (A)-L-valine (val), L-phenylalanine (phe) and DL-tryptophan (trp) (B) systems.

Results and Discussion

MAB, MA₂B and MA₂B₂ types of ternary complexes (Table 2) in addition to the binary species HA, MA, MA₂, HB, H₂B, MB, MB₂ and MB₃ (Table 1) are present in the six Schiff base complex systems under investigation.

Stability and structure of MAB complexes: The preferential formation of the ternary complexes over binary species can be illustrated by considering the stepwise formation constants of the various species formed. For Co^{II}-pyal (A)-val(B) system the scheme (Scheme 1) shows that for-

Table 1 Stability constants for proton, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} binary complexes with pyal (A), val, phe and trp (B)

Parameter	Co ^{II}				Ni ^{II}			
	pyal ^a	val ^b	phe ^b	trp ^b	pyal ^a	val ^b	phe ^b	trp ^b
log β _{HA}	3.84	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
log β _{MA}	1.75	-	-	-	1.98	-	-	-
log β _{MA₂}	3.45	-	-	-	3.90	-	-	-
log β _{HB}	-	2.24	2.23	2.20	-	-	-	-
log β _{H₂B}	-	9.65	9.31	9.43	-	-	-	-
log β _{MB}	-	4.44	4.45	4.46	-	5.26	5.15	5.05
log β _{MB₂}	-	7.98	8.01	8.02	-	9.12	9.10	12.05
log β _{MB₃}	-	9.71	9.73	9.75	-	12.35	12.35	12.10

^aRef. 9. ^bRef. 11.

mation of ternary species is favoured over that of the successive binary complexes. If we consider CoAB as a simple mixed ligand complex without interligand interaction, then the log β_{CoAB} calculated⁵ should be 6.1 log units, but the experimental value is 10.21 log units. This large enhancement arises from the presence of strong inter-ligand attractive forces between pyal and val, leading to the formation of a terdentate Schiff base ligand (AB), which can bind Co^{II}

Table 2 Stability constants for the ternary Schiff base complexes in the M(II)-pyal(A)-val, phe and trp(B) systems

Metal ion	ligand B	log β _{MAB}	log β _{MA₂B}	log β _{MA₂B₂}	log K _{MAB} ^{MA}	log K _{MAB} ^{MB}	log K _{MA₂B} ^{MAB}	log K _{MA₂B₂} ^{MAB}
Co ^{II}	val	10.21	12.22	15.96	8.46	5.77	2.01	8.77
	phe	10.11	12.09	15.87	8.36	5.66	1.98	8.64
	trp	10.09	12.32	15.93	8.34	5.63	2.23	8.87
Ni ^{II}	val	11.48	13.73	18.46	9.50	6.22	2.25	9.83
	phe	11.30	13.56	18.25	9.32	6.15	2.26	9.66
	trp	11.39	13.87	18.35	9.41	6.34	2.48	9.97

Scheme 1

through pyridine and imino nitrogens and carboxylato oxygen atoms. The resulting Schiff base complex Co(AB) is a stable one containing two five-membered chelate rings. The enhanced stability can be attributed in part to the fusion of two independent ring systems leading to the multi-ring formation by the same ligand (AB) due to enhanced entropy. The $\log \beta_{\text{Co(AB)}}$ values of 10.11 and 10.09 respectively, in Co^{II}-pyal(A)-phe and trp(B) systems are comparable to that of 10.21 in the Co^{II}-pyal(A)-val(B) system. This demonstrates the same type of binding in the Co(AB) species in all the three Co^{II}-pyal(A)-val, phe and trp(B) systems. This also indicates that the presence of phenyl group in the phe ligand and indole group in the trp ligand moiety exerts little steric influence on the formation of the ternary Schiff base complexes respectively in the Co^{II}-pyal(A)-phe and trp(B) systems.

NiAB species in the Ni^{II}-pyal(A)-val, phe and trp(B) systems also exhibit higher stability (Table 2). The $\log \beta_{\text{NiAB}}$ values obtained experimentally in these systems are respectively 11.48, 11.30 and 11.39. The statistically calculated⁵ values if they were simple mixed ligand complexes, are 6.81, 7.00 and 6.80 log units respectively. Hence it can be concluded that similar to CoAB, NiAB are also Schiff base complexes where the terdentate Schiff base (AB) is coordinated to Ni^{II} through all the three available donors forming a stable complex.

The species distribution diagrams where the metal : pyal concentration is kept at 1 : 1, show that M(AB) complex species are predominant between pH 7.0 and 8.0 accounting a maximum of 65–70% of the total metal ion concentration. However, in the 1 : 2 systems, this species is found to be present at a relatively lower concentration accounting a maximum of 35–40% in the pH range 6.5–7.4. The electronic spectrum of CoAB complex in the Co^{II}-pyal(A)-val (B) system was recorded at pH 7.5 in the 1 : 1 system. It shows an absorption maxima at 697 nm, which can be attributed to the $^4A_2(F) \rightarrow ^4A_1(P)$ transition of Co^{II} due to its tetrahedral geometry. The NiAB complex in the Ni^{II}-pyal (A)-val(B) system in its electronic spectrum measured at

pH 7.63 in the 1 : 1 system, exhibits λ_{max} at 680 nm. This corresponds to the $^3T_1(F) \rightarrow ^3T_1(P)$ transition of Ni^{II} in the tetrahedral environment of the ligand field. Thus both NiAB and CoAB can be assigned tetrahedral geometry, where three corners of the tetrahedron would be occupied by the three donors of the Schiff base ligand (AB) and a solvent water molecule takes up the fourth corner. The same structural characteristics have also been reported in the solid state⁴.

Stability and structure of MA₂B complexes : The experimental $\log \beta$ values for the CoA₂B species in Co^{II}-pyal (A)-val, phe and trp(B) systems are respectively 12.22, 12.09 and 12.32. If these species are considered to be simple mixed ligand complexes, then the calculated stability constant values⁵ should be 7.74, 7.76 and 7.76 log units respectively. This higher experimental values lead to the conclusion that the CoA₂B species is a Schiff base complex of the type Co(AB)A. The Schiff base (AB) is tridentate and the second pyal is bound⁹ through its pyridine nitrogen alone.

The experimental $\log \beta$ values for the NiA₂B species obtained in the Ni^{II}-pyal(A)-val, phe and trp(B) systems are 13.73, 13.56 and 13.87 respectively, while the calculated values on the assumption that NiA₂B complexes are simple mixed ligand species⁵ are respectively 8.76, 8.95 and 8.75. This shows that NiA₂B species are also Schiff base complexes of the type Ni(AB)A. The M(AB)A species have been found to be formed above pH 7.5, accounting a maximum of the 15% of the total metal ion in the form of the species in the 1 : 1 systems, and 30% in the 1 : 2 systems.

Stability and structure of MA₂B₂ complexes : The $\log \beta$ values obtained for the CoA₂B₂ species in the Co^{II}-pyal (A)-val, phe and trp(B) systems are respectively 15.96, 15.87 and 15.93. But the calculated values⁵, if they were simple mixed ligand complexes without interligand interaction are 11.73, 11.76 and 11.77 log units. Similarly, the experimental $\log \beta$ values for the NiA₂B₂ species in the Ni^{II}-pyal(A)-val, phe and trp(B) systems are 18.46, 18.25 and 18.35 respectively, whereas the calculated values for the simple mixed ligand complexes are 13.32, 13.70 and 13.30. The higher experimental values distinctly demonstrate that MA₂B₂ are Schiff base complexes. They can be represented as M(AB)₂, where both the Schiff base ligands are coordinated in a terdentate mode giving a coordination number six for the metal ion.

In the 1 : 1 systems, concentration of the Co(AB)₂ and Ni(AB)₂ species have been found to increase after pH 8.0, while in the 1 : 2 systems they are the predominant species between pH 7.2 and 8.5, reaching a maximum of 65% of the total metal ion. The electronic spectrum of Co(AB), com-

plex species in the Co^{II}-pyal(A)-val(B) system has been recorded at pH 8.16 in the 1 : 2 system. It shows two peaks at 826 and 496 nm. The higher energy peak is more intense. These absorption bands correspond to the transition of Co^{II} in an octahedral environment of the ligand field⁷. Again the electronic absorption spectrum of Ni(AB)₂ complex in the Ni^{II}-pyal(A)-val(B) system measured at pH 7.90 in the 1 : 2 system contains three λ_{max} values 897, 692 and 391 nm of which the last one is more intense. These peaks correspond to the transitions of the Ni^{II} in an octahedral ligand field.

Experimental

AnalaR grade metal nitrates were used. The pyal ligand (pure grade from Lancaster) was further purified by distilling twice under reduced pressure. The amino acid secondary ligands (puris, Fluka) were used. In the ternary Schiff base complex systems the equilibrium was attained slowly. Hence a batchwise titration procedure was adopted^{8,9}. Calculations were done with the aid of a computer program¹⁰ designed for the evaluation of Schiff base complex equilibria on a Wipro computer with Pentium, fixing the auxiliary data for the binary complexes under the present experimental conditions (Table 1) as non-refinable parameters. The equipments used for the electronic spectral measure-

ments have been described earlier⁹. All the experiments were carried out at 25° and an ionic strength of 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (KNO₃).

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